
Research

Design & fabrication of bismuth telluride (Bi₂Te₃) based small capacity peltier effect refrigerator

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Abstract: The most energy-consuming home appliances are refrigeration and air conditioner and for that reason, many researchers had carried out the performance of the refrigeration system. The main focus of this study is to obtain low energy consumption and enhancement of green refrigeration by using the thermoelectric effect technique. In this small capacity refrigerator, the Peltier effect technique is used to reduce the internal temperature. A thermoelectric plate of lightweight material Bismuth Telluride (Bi₂Te₃) material, strengthen and had lower thermal conductivity of 0.02 W/m K, is used having one hot side and another cold side. Heat moved from the internal hot side to the external cold side, resulting in temperature reduction in the internal volume of the refrigerator with help of the Peltier effect. In this thermoelectric refrigerator, a volume of 125L cooled and maintained the temperature range from 35°C to 20°C in near about 4 minutes and 35°C to 23°C in approximately 22 minutes without using internal load and without using internal load respectively. Furthermore, it is environmentally friendly and has low energy consumption. In addition, globally demand for refrigeration is increasing day by day and it is a great threat because the concentration of CO₂ has been increased in the atmosphere for a few years and it caused global warming and enhanced the effects of the other climate change.

Keywords: Refrigerator, Peltier effect, Eco-friendly, Bismuth Telluride, global warming

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Introduction

The conventional cooling system used now requires a refrigerant that undergoes a phase change in heat exchange and requires a compressor to compress the refrigerant [1]. The compressor needs more power and space. The refrigerant is not environmentally friendly [2]. Mini eco-friendly refrigerators are basically working on the Peltier effect and are used in cooling purposes [3]. Its also relieable due to use of less corrosive material [4].

Thermoelectric refrigeration is a phenomenon of extracting heat energy from an insulated box to lower temperature of the box below the ambient air temperature. Thermoelectric cooling utilizes a principle known as a "PELTIER" effect to push heat electronically [5].

The thermoelectric effect is used for many purposes, including power generation, miniature portable microcontrollers, air and refrigeration coolers. Refrigeration is defined in science as keeping temperature below the temperature of the atmosphere and lowering the temperature of objects [6]. Refrigeration provides temperature difference for food preservation and storage applications. Another requirement of refrigerators is the development of scientific equipment or its functions in a controlled-environment to obtain well founded results [7]. Nowadays, our world is faced with many harmful gases, such as carbon dioxide. Due to global warming and the factors that change our world’s climate, these gases are spread all over the world [8-9]. Thermoelectric refrigeration is a new refrigeration method, also known as an alternative refrigeration method

Thermoelectric refrigerators are a new option because they can convert electrical energy into valuable cooling, and usually playing a special role for energy challenging problems, rather than what thermo-electric refrigerators really need, mainly because developing countries require reliable life and having less maintenance [6,10]. The co-efficient of performance for the compression refrigerator reduces with the reduction of its volume. Therefore, when it is required to design a small capacity refrigerator. It is almost recommended to use a thermoelectric refrigerator, and having good control of space temperature is the main advantage of a thermoelectric refrigerator [11]. Therefore, thermoelectric refrigerators are ideal for food preservation applications and medicine cooling. Thermoelectric equipment has many uses, such as cooling sensitive parts such as power amplifiers and micro-processors in electronic systems and computers, and is also used in satellite or space applications to deal with extreme temperature edges in components under the sun [6,12].

In 1821 a scientist with name Thomas Seebeck discovered “Seebeck effect”. This is related to the generation of voltage along the conductors affected by the temperature gradient. As shown in Figure , if a temperature-gradient $\Delta T = (T_{cold} - T_{hot})$ Applied to conductor, electromotive force (EMF), $\Delta V = (V_2 - V_1)$, will happened between the hot and cold sides due to phonon drag and charge carrier diffusion. The whole system is in a semi equilibrium state, the chemical potential caused by the concentration is balanced by the built-in electrostatic potential, which is the Seebeck voltage. The Seebeck coefficient α of the conductor is defined as [13] and shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Seebeck effect

In 1834, a famous scientist Peltier discovered that the phenomenon of thermo-electric cooling depends on the Peltier effect. The Peltier coefficient is a measure for the amount of heat which is carried by the holes and electrons. There is a proportional relationship between the heat and current. The Peltier-coefficient, which is a constant of proportionality, and its relationship is given by;

$$\pi = Q / I$$

Where Q is the heat flow and I is the current. Let's suppose there are two different materials which are combined together as shown in Figure 2. Each material has different peltier coefficients. The heat flow at the junction produces abrupt changes. The heat is produced by the excess amount of energy which is released into lattices. The cooling is produced by the insufficient energy provided by the lattice. The polarity of the current helps to control the direction of heat transfer. Reversible electrical-polarity can change the direction of transfer; thereby changing is sign of heat-absorption/release. The Peltier-effect is basically a working principle behind a thermo-electric module (also known as a Peltier cooling device) or refrigerator, which can be used for transferring of heat from one point of the device to the other [13,14].

Figure 2 Peltier effect

Experimental procedure

Thermoelectric Material: The best and simplest composite thermoelectric material on the market for refrigeration near room temperature is bismuth tellurized. In 1950s Bi_2Te_3 was developed. One of the most interesting aspects of Bi_2Te_3 is that its Seebeck coefficient depends on its composition, as shown in Figure 3. The undoped Bi_2Te_3 (equivalent to 60 atomic percentage of Te) is of type p and has a Seebeck coefficient of approximately $230 \mu\text{V} / \text{K}$. As the Te concentration increases, the Seebeck coefficient gradually decreases to zero and then changes sign to become negative (n-type) [15]. The maximum ZT for p-type and n-type Bi_2Te_3 crystalline materials (non-alloys) at room temperature is approximately 0.75 and 0.86, respectively. Crystalline Bi_2Te_3 ZT can be improved by alloying. The three compounds Bi_2Te_3 , Sb_2Te_3 , and Bi_2Se_3 are completely soluble. Adding Sb_2Te_3 or Bi_2Se_3 to Bi_2Te_3 improves ZT, primarily by lowering the lattice thermal conductivity, but does not significantly degrade the electronic properties. The results show that for p-type and n-type, the optimal components for thermoelectric cooling are usually $\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{Sb}_{1.5}\text{Te}_3$ and $\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_{3-0.7}\text{Se}_{0.3}$, respectively. Figure summarizes commonly used Bi_2Te_3 -based alloys with the highest ZT of about 1.1[13,16].

Figure 3 Thermo-electric figure of merit ZT of n- and p-type Bi₂Te₃-based alloys

The quality factor: The quality factor, Z is a method used to evaluate the performance of a thermoelectric device where it is equal to:

$$Z = \frac{\alpha^2}{\rho k}$$

Where ρ is the resistivity in ohms and k is the thermal conductivity in W / mK. Higher Z values can be obtained from higher α or lower ρ and k values [17]. These variables depend on the type of material at the specified temperature and can be displayed as a dimensionless number ZT. Therefore, materials with higher ZT values should be used for higher TE performance. Since these values are temperature related, the quality factor is temperature related. Therefore, P-type and N-type materials have different quality factors, and the average value is used to determine the overall quality of the material. In thermoelectric coolers, bismuth telluride (Bi₂Te₃) is one of the most widely used materials in such applications due to its high quality factor at room temperature. Other bulk materials such as lead telluride (PbTe) can also be used in his TE modules, especially for high temperature and thermoelectric generator (TEG) applications. Figure 4 (a) shows the relationship between ZT and temperature for the quality coefficients of various p-type semiconductors. Bi₂Te₃ shows the highest output in the temperature range (0 to 200°C) associated with electronic cooling. Similar results are shown in Figure 4 (b) for n-type semiconductors [13,18].

Figure 4: ZT for p-type and n-type thermoelectric materials

Design and construction

The main components that are required in the design fabrication of small capacity of refrigerator are given below.

Power supply

A power supply is an electrical device which is used to supply electric current to a machine, its main function is that to give a suitable load at which machine can work effectively and give maximum output, in this refrigerator power supply convert AC current to DC and with the help of this controlled the cooling of Peltier device and fan speed as shown in Figure 5 (a) Power supply.

Temperature Sensor (thermistor)

Temperature-sensor is an electrical machine which indicated temperature in a numeric way, by the help of this device as shown in Figure 5 (b) Temperature Sensor (thermistor). It can be easily measure the refrigerator cooling temperature and take full control of its performance. If any fault is occurring the refrigerator can't give the desired output cooling temperature and temperature sensor sense it and necessary steps are taken to maintenance of this refrigerator and get output performance. It is an important device that provides information about the cooling rate of the chamber and also helps to calculate the efficiency of the device (ie thermoelectric refrigerator).

Heat Resistant Sheet

Heat resistant sheet or heat resistant fabric is a combination of much material with one same property is thermal insulation. Its main work is to resist outside heat and make constant inside temperature, it is made of mainly tantalum carbide which can handle temperature almost 3000 degree Celsius as shown in Figure 5 (c) Heat Resistant Sheet. Tantalum carbide (TaC) are refractory ceramics, means they can be best material of resistant to heat, in this thermoelectric refrigerator box is coated with this sheet which make the inside temperature cool by control the outside heating effects.

Fin

A fin is a surface extending from an object, which increases the heat transfer rate to the surrounding environment by increasing convection as shown in Figure 5 (d) Fin. Adding fins to the object will increase the surface area and is an economical way to solve the heat transfer problem. The shape of the fin must be optimized to maximize the heat transfer density when the space and materials used on the fin surface are limited. The cooling rate depends on the surface area of the heat sink exposed to the environment. In thermoelectric refrigerators, fins are used for the cold side and the hot side. Heat sinks are used with cooling fans to draw more heat from the cold side to the hot side. The fins on the hot side are used to increase the surface area of the fan, thereby reducing overheating and making the equipment work efficiently.

Silicon Sealant

Silicon sealant is a type of gel used for sealing, bonding, gasketing, insulating, waterproofing the machine. It has a different chemical make-up from other organic polymer-based adhesives. Silicones exhibit almost effective characteristics including, less thermal conductivity, less chemical reactivity and minor toxicity. It's used for sealing the holes and other unclosed joints as shown in Figure 5 (e) Silicon Sealant.

Peltier Module

Peltier module is a solid-state device which is used for cooling or heating purposes. It is made of 2 ceramic plates as shown in Figure 5 (f) Peltier Module and in between semiconductor (n-type and p-type) is set in it. When current is passing through 2 junction it will work. Heating is moved from one side to another side by this process its one side is become cold and other side become so hot. It's used inside the refrigerator for cooling.

Refrigerator Box

It is just like a normal box which helps to make a cooling chamber as shown in Figure 5 (g) Refrigerator Box. Basically, the refrigeration box is made of steel sheet which is insulated from outside with the heat resistant sheet, jumbo Lon form and polyurethane. It also makes to hold to screw on it. It is useful because it is more cheaply than other refrigeration box. The dimensions of the refrigeration box that used are 500×500×500mm.

Polyurethane

Polyurethane are one of the versatile plastics materials as shown in Figure 5 (h) Polyurethane. It can be easily shaped. Polyurethane is formed by the reaction of polyols [it's an alcohols with more than two reactive hydroxyl families per molecule] and diisocyanates or polymeric isocyanates in the presence of suitable additives and catalysts. Because of this material it makes it lightweight, strengthens and had lower thermal conductivity 0.02 W/m K. In thermoelectric refrigerator box is insulated with this form which makes our refrigerator cooling performance better for long times when there is short fall on power.

Heat Sink

The aluminum heat-sink is usually in contact with the hottest side of the thermoelectric module. When connect the positive and negative leads of the module to the positive and negative terminals of a DC power supply, heat is dissipated from the hot side of the module and the heat sink facilitates heat dissipation. Heat-sinks are usually in the middle of the heat dissipation process, where heat flows into the radiator before being transferred to an external medium. Typical heat sinks include natural convection, forced convection, and fluid cooling, depends on the size of the refrigerator as shown in Figure 5 (i) Heat Sink.

(a) Power supply

(b) Temperature Sensor (thermistor)

(c) Heat Resistant Sheet

(d) Fin

(e) Silicon Sealant

(f) Peltier Module

(g) Refrigerator

(h) Polyurethane

(i) Heat Sink

Figure 5 Components of Peltier Effect Refrigerator

Assembly

In this section the process of assembly of different parts is discussed.

- **Manufacturing of Refrigeration chamber:** first of all make a chamber type box for refrigerator. First, polyurethane is used for cooling controlled refrigeration. After that, double-sided insulation is completed. The outside is insulated with a thick steel plate of 22gauge and the outside with a 1 mm-thick aluminum plate. Insulation is intended to cool the box properly and prevent it from radiating heat to the surrounding environment.
- **Cutting for fin fan assembly:** After making chamber, cut the box from back side to the appropriate size so that fin-fan assembly can be fitted inside.
- **Drilling for making holes:** Drilling is completed with two fins, the hotter fin and the colder fin. Drilling is to secure the two fins together. The two fins are firmly fixed to the jig to make holes, and the holes are punched very accurately with a drilling machine.
- **Mounting of thermoelectric Module:** Careful use of the cutter is required to install the module. Wipe off any dust or grease on the surface of the fins that connect to the Peltier module with a thermal grease film such as alcohol. Then use glue to connect the thermoelectric module to the fins.
- **Screws Tightening:** After the thermo-electric module is inserted b/w the fins, the two fins are screwed into the pre-drilled holes. Tighten the screws tightly and cut off the excess screws.
- **Fitting of Fin Fan Assembly:** when screwing is done in the fins, then connect fans to them after that attach the entire assembly from the back side of the refrigerator. Then assembly is climbed with the cold fins inside the chamber and the hot fins outside the chamber. Peltier module should be between the two fins.
- **Power Supply Selection:** The circuit-controller is now climbed on the back side of chamber. The power supply uses a circuit controller. Both fan and the Peltier-module wired to a circuit-controller. The black line is for positive pole and red line is for negative pole. Here, we are using a DC-12V power supply.

Working and Basic Layout

In this section the discussion is about the layout and construction of the multipurpose empanelment form (MEF). The layout of the MEF consists of a simple Thermal box which is used as a Cooling chamber. The inner part of the box is covered with the steel sheet of thickness 1mm. The outer-side of the box is insulated a wooden-sheet with the thickness of 4mm. The block diagram of the MEF is given below the dimensions of the MEF Refrigerator have been described in the Figure 6. The dimensions are 500×500×500 mm. On the back of the refrigerator is the fin fan assembly which is the basis of cooling in the thermo-electric refrigerator. In this figure W_1 , L_1 & B_1 represent the width, length and thickness of peltier device and W_2 , L_2 & B_2 represent the width, length and thickness of fin fan. There are two fin fan assembly one at the hot side and another on the cold side.. Between the both fin-fan assembly there is a Peltier device which is the cooling device of this thermo-electric refrigerator. The Peltier device is connected to the circuit controller which acts as a DC power supplier. As a result of Peltier effect one side of the Peltier device becomes cool and others become hot. This is deeply described in circuit diagram shown below. The complete manufactured Peltier effect refrigerator and its front, internal and back views are shown in Figure 7 (a), (b) and (c) respectively.

Figure 6: Basic Layout

(a) Front View

(b) Internal View

(c) Back View

Figure 7: Peltier effect refrigerator

Calculation and Result:

Overall Heat Transfer Co-efficient of a Composite Wall

$$U = \frac{1}{R_{(total)}}$$

Where

U = overall heat transfer co-efficient

$$R_{(total)} = R_1 + R_2 + R_3$$

$$R_1 = R_{steel} = 13.38 \text{ m}^2\text{k/w}$$

$$R_2 = R_{diamond \text{ jamlom}} = 0.025 \text{ m}^2\text{k/w}$$

$$R_3 = R_{steel} = 13.38 \text{ m}^2\text{k/w}$$

$$R_{(\text{total})} = 13.38 + 0.025 + 13.38 = 26.785$$

$$U = \frac{1}{26.785} = 0.03733 \text{ w/m}^2\text{k}$$

It is used to find out the Overall Heat Transfer Co-efficient how much heat will be conducted through over a series of resistant mediums.

Heat flow rate/ transmission load

$$Q = \frac{T_1 - T_3}{R_{(\text{total})}}$$

Q = heat flow rate

T₁ = internal temperature = 30 °C

T₃ = outer temperature = 10 °C

$$Q = \frac{30 - 10}{26.785} = 0.74 \text{ w}$$

It is used to find out the transmission load how much heat will flow to over wall

Product load

$$Q = \frac{M \times C_p \times \Delta T}{3600}$$

Q = Heat supplied by introduction of new goods into space which are at high temperature

Specific heat capacity = 3.65 kJ/kg °C

T_{enter} = Temperature of apple entering = 5 °C

T_{store} = Temperature inside the fridge = 1 °C

New Product Daily = M = 100 kg

$$Q = \frac{100 \times 3.65 \times (5 - 1)}{3600} = 0.406 \text{ KWh/day} = 40.6 \text{ Wh/day}$$

It is used to find out the total product load per day and it consists of all the heat gain occurring due to the product refrigeration space.

Product Respiration

$$Q = \frac{M \times \text{Resp}}{3600}$$

Specific heat capacity = 3.65 kJ/kg °C

Respiration heat = 1.9 kJ/kg day

Total product = M = 120

$$Q = \frac{120 \times 1.9}{3600} = 0.0633 \text{ KWh/day} = 63.33 \text{ Wh/day}$$

It is used to find out the total product respiration per day.

Equipment load

$$Q = \frac{\text{Fans} \times \text{Time} \times \text{Wattage(watts)}}{1000}$$

We find the Calculation of heat rejected or absorbed of fan motors

Number of fans = 3

Wattage of fans = 200w

Hours of use per day = 14

1000 = conversion watts to kw

$$Q = \frac{3 \times 14 \times 200}{1000} = 8.4 \text{ kwh/day}$$

It is used to find out the total equipment load per day.

Observation

(a) For No load condition:

Test was carried out in a room having 32°C atmospheric temperature.

Table: 1 Variation of temperature w.r.t time without loading condition.

Time (sec)	0	6	8	11	14	27	45	64	91	144	180	238
Temperature (C°)	31	30	29	28	27	26	25	24	23	22	21	20

Graphical presentation without load

Graph: 1 Temperature vs Time (without load)

From the above graph-1 it can be inferred that

- 1) For decrease in temperature from 31o C to 27o C, cooling rate is fast it is near about linear.
- 2) From 27o C to 22o C, time required for cooling is increased and thus cooling rate is moderate.
- 3) Beyond 22o C, Cooling rate becomes low and take much more time for cooling.

(b) For load condition:

For the load condition 0.2736 liter of water is filled inside the Bottle. Test was carried out in a room having 34o C atmospheric temperature.

Table: 2 Variation of temperature with time (Load)

Time (sec)	0	127	131	243	365	501	676	920	1272
Temperature (C°)	31	30	29	28	27	26	25	24	23

Graphical presenataion with load

Graph: 2 Temperature vs Time

From the above graph-2 it can be inferred that

- 1) in start for decrease in temperature from 31°C to 30°C, cooling rate is low.
- 2) From 30 °C to 23 °C, time required for cooling is increased with linearly increasing of time.
- 3) Beyond 23 °C, Cooling rate becomes low and take much more time for cooling.

Conclusion

Its a pure eco-friendly multipurpose refrigerating project and portable successfully designed system which fulfills the proposed targets. Its working principle can also be used for air conditioning. The present design of refrigerator can be used only for maintaining a particular temperature. There are no moving parts and no maintenance is required. There is no use of any refrigerant and compressor. In this work, a thermoelectric refrigerator is developed that can cool a volume of 125L and maintained the temperature range from 35°C to 20°C. this observation is done in two ways. First when there was no load the temperature down from 35°C -20°C in just 4 to 5 minutes. On the other hand when the load is applied then it takes long time about 26 minutes to reach at the same temperature range. it can be done with the help of the Peltier effect using lightweight Polyurethane material, strengthen and had lower thermal- conductivity of 0.02 W/m. It takes a short time to cool this volume. The main objective is that to obtain low energy consumption and enhancement of refrigeration effect. It can be work at solar power easily. Globally demand for refrigeration is increasing day by day and it is a great threat because the concentration of CO₂ has been increased in the atmosphere for few years and it caused global warming and enhancing effects of the other climate change. The system is unable to handle fluctuations in load. In the presence of these harmful environmental problem this refrigerator is much better for refrigeration at small level. Using the peltier effect it can be modify for higher level.

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